

Successful surgical management of fibroma tumor in rats

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Abstract

An adult male Wistar rat, aged two years, presented with an abnormal growth in the central abdominal region. Surgical treatment was performed under general anesthesia, involving excision of the mass. Histopathological examination diagnosed a fibroma, characterized by the presence of coarse bundles of collagen fibers interspersed with individual fibroblasts. Hematological evaluation included measurements of red blood cell count (RBC), white blood cell count (WBC), hemoglobin concentration (HBG), hematocrit (HCT), mean corpuscular volume (MCV), mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH), mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC), and platelet count (PLT). All parameters were generally within physiological reference ranges. In our case, the aged male Wistar rat, underwent successful surgical treatment for a spontaneous benign fibroma during healthy aging, ultimately improving physiological comfort and recovery. There is a lack of published studies addressing this issue, which could shed light on the frequency of fibroma occurrence in rats across different strains and age groups..

Keywords: *Fibroma, Aged rat Male Wistar rat, Surgical excision*

Introduction

A fibroma is a benign tumor primarily composed of connective collagen fibers and fibroblasts. It is typically slow-growing, non-metastatic, and may appear as a nodule, growth, or thickening on the skin or in the subcutis.¹ A wide range of etiological factors contribute to the development of fibromas, most commonly chronic irritation, various types of trauma, essential genetic factors, viral infections (e.g., poxviruses, papillomaviruses), and ultimately hormonal changes.² Two common types of fibromas are known in the skin of humans and animals: hard fibromas (dermatofibromas), which consist of many fibers and few cells, and soft fibromas (skin tags), which are composed of loosely connected cells with less fibrous tissue.^{3,4}

In addition to humans^{5,6}, fibromas have been documented in a wide range of animals, including wildlife (deer, rabbits, squirrels, raccoons, moose, birds)⁷, domesticated animals such as horses⁸, camels⁹, cattle^{2,3}, especially in older dogs (Dobermans and Golden Retrievers)^{10,11} and rodents, such as rats¹².

Rats are genetically predisposed to a high incidence of tumors.¹³ In dermal fibromas in rats, the incidence is slightly higher in males (4.5%) compared to females (3%).¹⁴ Overall, there is insufficient literature available to clarify the unknowns regarding the frequency of fibroma occurrence in rats across different strains and age groups.

The aim of this study was to describe a case of fibroma in a two-year-old male Wistar rat, localized in the abdo-

minal region, and its surgical treatment.

Case Presentation

An intact male Wistar rat, two years old and weighing 485 grams (Figure 1), was found to have an abnormal growth located in the central abdominal region. The rat was housed individually in a cage with a temperature of 22 °C, air humidity of 60%, and a 12-hour light/dark cycle. It consumed standard conventional rat feed.

Figure 1a, 1b Visible abnormal mass in the central abdominal region of the male rat.

During the clinical examination, the rat showed no signs of general health disturbance, consistent with its age. The mass located in the central ventral part of the body was initially suspected to be an abscess. Upon palpation, the mass was smooth and firm in consistency. The rat did not show signs of pain during the examination. The differential diagnosis of abscess was excluded after aspiration of the mass. Radiographic imaging ruled out possible metastatic formations.

Surgical excision of the mass followed, with the rat placed under general anesthesia using 5 mg/kg of 2% xylazine hydrochloride (2% Xylazin, CpPharma, Bergdorf, Germany) and 50 mg/kg of ketamine hydrochloride (International B.V., Netherlands), administered intramuscularly.

The rat was operated on in a dorsal recumbent position using routine surgical techniques, strictly adhering to aseptic and antiseptic principles. The tumorous formation was removed. Postoperative skin healing was supported with chlorine dioxide (ClO₂) at a concentration of 120 ppm (ITR d.o.o., Bosnia and Herzegovina) 15, applied as a spray twice daily for fourteen days. The patient was housed in a separate cage with clean bedding. Pellet food and water were available ad libitum. The entire postoperative period proceeded smoothly, without complications, in accordance with the rat's age.

Additionally, a peripheral blood sample was taken for standard hematological analysis via tail vein puncture into EDTA vacutainers. Postoperative hematological parameters were obtained using the automated hematology analyzer Mindray BC-20S. Leukocyte cell types were differentiated, and numerical values were expressed as percentages after analyzing 1000 cells. Differentiated cells included: lymphocytes (%), monocytes (%), neutrophils (%), basophils (%), and acidophiles (%), using a Motic Type 102 M light binocular microscope at 1000x magnification.

The tumor tissue sample was fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin, dehydrated, embedded in paraffin, sectioned at 5 µm, mounted on a glass slide, and stained with

hematoxylin and eosin for microscopic evaluation.

Table 1. Hematological parameters of the rat after surgical procedure.

Parameters	Unit	Results	Ref - Ranges
WBC	10 ⁹ /L	8.30	1.90-13.80
Lymphocytes	%	77.5	75.8-92.9
Neutrophils	%	19.5	3,5-18.7
Monocytes	%	2.5	0.5-3.4
Basophils	%	0.0	0.2-0.6
Acidophiles	%	0.5	0.0-0.6
RBC	10 ¹² /L	9.44	4.82-9.80
HGB	g/L	161	110-170
HCT	%	52	27-46
MCV	fL	55	50-67
MCH	pg	17	16-25
MCHC	g/L	310	310-390
RDW-CV	%	0.14	1.1-1.5
RDW-SD	fL	31.2	25-40
PLT	10 ⁹ /L	1147	250-1400
MPV	fL	6.9	5.1-8.2
PDW	f/L	15	12-17.5
PCT	ml/L	7.96	2-8.2
P-LCC	10 ⁹ /L	465	100-580
P-LCR	%	0.40	0,22-0,57

Figure 2. a) The skin fibroma occupies the full thickness of the dermis, sparing only the superficial portion containing hair follicles (blue arrow), eccrine (green arrow), and apocrine glands (red arrow); magnification 50x. b) The fibroma is composed of coarse bundles of collagen fibers (red arrow), between which individual fibroblasts (indigo arrow) and occasional eosinophilic leukocytes are present (blue arrow); magnification 400x.

Discussion and Conclusion

Histopathological examination of the tumor revealed a high degree of dermal involvement by this benign formation, with clear evidence that only the superficial portion of the dermis, containing hair follicles, eccrine, and apocrine glands, was practically spared by the benign tumorous mass. Furthermore, in our case, the fibroma was composed of coarse bundles of collagen fibers, between which individual fibroblasts and occasional eosinophilic leukocytes were present.

Understanding the histopathology of benign tumors is a key aspect in establishing an accurate diagnosis and

making informed decisions regarding the treatment of affected animals.¹⁶

Fibromas can appear on any part of the body but are most commonly found on the neck, head, and limbs of animals.¹² Depending on their size and location, they may adversely affect vision, feeding, breathing, and movement. Growths in the form of fibromas are generally self-limiting and tend to regress spontaneously as affected animals develop an immune response.¹¹

In our case, the fibroma was localized in the central abdominal region. Its prominent visibility not only posed an aesthetic concern but primarily hindered the

animal's ability to rest or sleep comfortably on its abdomen. Scratches on the abdominal fibroma presented a potential risk for secondary bacterial infections. This is particularly significant in immunocompromised patients, where untreated fibromas may progress and negatively impact internal organs through compression. Given that our patient was of geriatric age, this was a decisive factor prompting cautious surgical excision of the fibroma, which was successfully completed without adverse outcomes for the patient.

The literature available for comparison with our case is very limited, with the exception of the case described by Parmar et al.¹², who reported a fibroma located in the neck region. Unlike fibromas, adenofibromas are more prevalent in the rat population, especially among females. A common characteristic of both benign tumors is that they are routinely and successfully treated surgically in a high percentage of cases, although both have a tendency to recur.¹⁷

Hematological parameters related to the total red blood cell count (RBC), RDW-CV and RDW-SD, as well as volume (MCV), hemoglobin content (HGB), and other erythrocyte indices (MCH, MCHC), remained within physiological reference ranges, except for hematocrit (HCT), which was elevated. Since the total RBC count was within normal limits but close to the upper physiological threshold, and MCV was also elevated, the increase in HCT could be associated with possible insufficient water intake during the pre- and postoperative period. Platelet count (PLT) and other platelet-related parameters (MPV, PDW, PCT, P-LCC, and P-LCR) remained stable. The total white blood cell count (WBC), as well as all leukocyte subtypes, were within physiological limits, indicating no active inflammatory processes in the patient.

In our case, the patient, a two-year-old male Wistar rat, underwent successful surgical treatment for a spontaneous benign fibroma during healthy aging, ultimately improving overall physiological comfort and recovery. There is a lack of published studies addressing this issue, which could help clarify the unknowns regarding the frequency of fibroma occurrence in rats across different strains and age groups.

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